

HEMP AND RICE STRAW VALORIZATION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUSTAINABLE ANTIOXIDANT-CELLULOSIC BASED CRYOGELS AND AEROGELS

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Abstract: *One of the strategies to ensure food safety is to extend the shelf life of food, therefore minimizing food losses and wastage. The main challenge in food production is to maintain food safety and improve nutritional and sensory quality in an affordable way. Shelf life depends on many factors, including the quality of raw materials, product formulation, type of preparation, packaging and storage conditions (Hosseini et al. 2020). Active food packaging has been proposed as a potential solution to achieve this goal. Among other desired functionalities, many active packaging concepts involve the release of antioxidants substances onto the food surface, as a way of improving the stability of oxidation-sensitive food products (Gomez-Estaca et al., 2014). The negative effects of oxidation on the nutritional and organoleptic properties of foods include: i) reduction in nutritional value due to destruction of essential fatty acids, proteins and lipid-soluble vitamins (A, D, E and K); ii) reduction in caloric value; iii) formation of rancidity (off-flavors); and iv) color changes due to darkening of fats and oils or degradation of pigments (Han et al., 2018).*

Mainly due to environmental concerns, novel active packaging concepts are being developed using biodegradable food packaging materials combined with natural preservatives. Therefore, the use of biopolymers, such as cellulose, has been proposed as a packaging constituent. Cellulose and its derivatives are attracting considerable attention due to their biocompatibility and environmental sustainability. Cellulose is a low-cost material with suitable mechanical properties and an excess demand in the global market. There is a large amount of agricultural waste and many processes need to be initiated to

make use of this waste. For example, some of the methods used in the fabrication of cellulose-based food packaging include solution casting, layer-by-layer assembly, extrusions, coatings, polymeric hydrogels, spraying, nano-emulsions, liposomes and adsorption (Liu et al., 2021).

*In this respect, hemp (*Cannabis sativa*) is an easy-to-grow plant that, by its very nature, does not require fertilisers or herbicides. It also contains 40-77% cellulose, depending on the growing conditions (Stevulova et al. 2014). Consequently, hemp can be used as a source of cellulose and other value-added compounds useful in the food packaging industry. One application in the meat industry is the production of absorbent pads that aim to reduce the exuded fluids from the product and, therefore, reduce the free water available for microorganisms (Castrica et al. 2020). In the present study, with the aim of developing antioxidant absorbent pads, hemp cellulose was used as a raw material for the production of aerogels and cryogels produced by supercritical drying and freeze-drying, respectively, which were then impregnated with an antioxidant extract from rice straw. As it is known that supercritical CO₂ produces aerogels with hairy beads, men while freeze-drying shoed a sheet-like morphology. Thus, the structure can influence the mechanical properties of the material and the water sorption capacity. The antioxidant extract was obtained as a by-product during the extraction of cellulose from rice straw through alkaline hydrolysis. The antioxidant capacity evaluated as the percentage of β-carotene bleaching inhibition showed high antioxidant activity (50.42%) in contrast to butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) used as a reference antioxidant (77.96%).*

To evaluate the development of hemp cellulose-based absorbent pads, the obtained aerogels and cryogels were further characterized to understand the effect of the drying method. First, both materials maintained their integrity when immersed in water, indicating that the hydrophobization of the cellulose during oxidation and homogenization was successful. In addition, the water sorption test showed that the cryogels and aerogels were able to absorb approximately 1.9 times their initial weight, indicating that both are good candidates for use as absorbent pads. However, aerogels presented significant shrinkage, when exposed to 100% RH, whereas cryogels remain almost the original size. On the other hand, TGA analysis showed that aerogels exhibited a shift in degradation peaks to higher temperatures. This demonstrates that aerogels have higher thermal stability than cryogels. Similarly, during compression tests aerogels did showed higher values than cryogels in the same compressive deformation

percentage, indicating that they are materials with higher resistance. The obtained materials differed in their density, compressibility, and water sorption. In addition, both materials were impregnated with the antioxidant extract, and the antioxidant capacity of the materials was evaluated. Thus, as a result of valorization strategies of hemp logs and rice straw residues, not only a food packaging material was developed but also a potential antioxidant delivery system.

Keywords: cryogels, aerogels, antioxidant, hemp, valorization

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